

Effect of moisture regime on rice yields in Alfisols and Vertisols

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A greenhouse experiment studied the effect of different moisture regimes on

growth and yield of rice Jaya in lateritic (Alfisol) and medium black (Vertisol) soils, two important types in the warm and humid agroclimatic region of Maharashtra State, India.

Three moisture regimes were maintained: half the maximum water-holding capacity, soil saturation, and soil submergence.

All treatments received 100 kg N and 50 kg P₂O₅/ha.

The optimum moisture regime was soil saturation in Alfisol, and soil submergence in Vertisol (see table). In Alfisol, the crop matured in 131 days in all moisture regimes. In Vertisol, days to maturity decreased as moisture increased. ■

Effect of moisture regimes on yield and yield-contributing characters of rice variety Jaya on 2 soils in Maharashtra, India.^a

Moisture regime ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle no.	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (g/pot)		Grain-to-straw ratio	Days to maturity	Harvest index (%)
				Grain	Straw			
<i>Alfisol</i>								
M1	77	4	24.9	6.15	6.75	0.91	131	44.89
M2	82	4	28.0	7.51	6.65	1.12	131	50.44
			(12.23)	(22.11)	(-1.48)			
M3	84	4	27.0	6.11	7.45	0.82	131	41.59
			(8.26)	(-0.65)	(10.37)			
<i>Vertisol</i>								
M1	87	9.5	20.2	7.82	20.50	0.38	142	24.52
M2	90	11.5	20.5	11.90	23.50	0.50	138	30.65
			(1.53)	(52.17)	(15.76)			
M3	105	13.5	22.2	18.53	27.40	0.67	131	36.15
			(10.06)	(136.95)	(34.97)			

^aMean of 2 replications. Figures in parentheses = % increase over M1. ^bM1 = half maximum water-holding capacity, M2 = soil saturation, and M3 = soil submergence.

Environment and its influence

Effects of environment on yields of 8 dryland rice cultivars in São Paulo, Brazil

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Study of genotype (G) × environment (E) interactions can lead to an evaluation of the yield stability of different genotypes, providing information for use in breeding programs. Eight rice cultivars were studied in 3 seasons (1974-77) in 21 environments of São Paulo State. The research design was an 8 × 8 Latin square.

The expected mean square component for G × E interactions was estimated by a pooled analysis of variance for yield and environment, taken 2 by 2, 3 by 3, . . . , E by E, in each season. Locations with similar performances in all seasons were pooled into two groups:

Homogenous subregions suggested for dryland rice in São Paulo State, Brazil.